

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Interannual Rainfall Variability in West Africa: Reconstruction based on Atmospheric Circulation Patterns

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Abstract

The West African Monsoon, known for its significant rainfall variability, led to the Sahel drought from 1968 to the 1990s, followed by a recovery in rainfall since the 1990s. In response to such variability, this study introduces a statistical approach for reconstructing interannual rainfall variability across seven rainfall regimes, each representing unique climatic zones in West Africa. Initially, a robust catalogue of daily atmospheric circulation pattern classifications over West Africa is established, based on pre-selected variables from the ERA5 reanalysis and using k-means clustering. Subsequently, the annual occurrence frequencies of these circulation pattern classifications, along with the annual rainfall conditions in the rainfall regimes, serve as inputs in a multi-class logistic regression model. This model is designed to identify dry, normal, and wet years, relative to the climatology. The rainfall regimes are determined using k-means clustering and a quality-controlled dataset from 971 rainfall stations, with daily observations ranging from 1959 to 2010. These regimes vary from the Sahelian belt, characterized by a short rainy season, to tropical regions exhibiting a bimodal rainfall regime. After comprehensive predictor screening of specific West African Monsoon patterns, such as the Tropical Easterly Jet and the African Easterly Jet, six variables at four different pressure levels under a running split-sampling cross-validation, the best models achieve an average proportion correct of 0.57 and a positive Peirce skill score for all regions over West Africa. This shows the performance in reconstructing dry, normal, and wet years for the different rainfall regimes in West Africa. Therefore, this study provides a statistical tool for the reconstruction of annual rainfall anomalies in this challenging region.

KEY WORDS

West Africa, rainfall, circulation patterns, k-means, logistic regression

1 | INTRODUCTION

The West African Monsoon (WAM) is one of the world's most complex regional climate systems, affecting key surface fluxes including rainfall, across a broad range of spatial and temporal scales (Nicholson 2001 2009, Lafore et al. 2011, Fink et al. 2016, Nicholson et al. 2018). Rainfall-related extremes and disasters in this region, such as the recent Nigeria floods in 2022 (Tunde 2022) or the Sahel droughts of the 1970s and 1980s (Hagos and Cook 2008), highlight the substantial vulnerabilities of both urban and rural communities (Paeth et al. 2011, Epule et al. 2013, Engel et al. 2017, Maranan et al. 2019, Atiah et al. 2023). To mitigate the impacts of natural disasters, accurate local-scale rainfall information is crucial for providing reliable warnings of extreme events and for numerous other applications. The existing methods employed by national weather services in West Africa exhibit various limitations, e.g., in the domain of seasonal rainfall forecasting (Bliefernicht et al. 2019). Moreover, state-of-the-art general circulation models (GCMs) fail to provide accurate local-scale rainfall information for West Africa, as shown by Vogel et al. (2018) in their assessment of global numerical weather prediction models. In contrast, GCMs demonstrate good performances in capturing regional-scale atmospheric phenomena such as the West African heat low or the AEWs in this challenging region (Ngoungue Langue et al. 2021, Bliefernicht et al. 2022a). To bridge this disparity, innovative statistical downscaling methods and strategies are essential (Maraun et al. 2010, Maraun and Widmann 2017). In this context, statistical techniques that use circulation patterns (CPs) have emerged as a promising approach, as shown by their diverse applications

across various regions of the world over recent decades (Moron et al. 2008b, Rust et al. 2013, Batté et al. 2018, Böker et al. 2023). In this study, the approach is tested for the annual areal rainfall amount of rainfall zones whose spatial extent is similar to the scales often used in climate predictions or seasonal forecasts (Bliefernicht et al. 2019). Although the current approach does not downscale the GCM output in the sense of providing higher spatiotemporal information, the statistical methods used here are based on the downscaling procedures.

Although the potential of CP-based statistical techniques is evident, its application in monsoon regions has been less explored. In the WAM region, relatively few studies have explored the relationship between CP classifications and local meteorological variables. Moron et al. (2008a) employed a k-means cluster analysis to classify regional circulation in the Western Sahel, focusing on its influence on rainfall in Senegal. This classification considered three wind levels (200, 700, and 925 hPa) during the months of July to September. Subsequently, these CPs were utilized in a downscaling method that performed well in capturing the interannual variability of rainfall, including the frequency and mean duration of dry and wet spells (Moron et al. 2008b). Guèye et al. (2011) identified nine CPs to account for Senegal's daily atmospheric circulation variability, primarily focusing on AEWs and the Saharan Heat Low (SHL). Camberlin et al. (2020) determined six types of intense rainfall events in southern West Africa, noting westward signals at the 700 hPa wind field. Moron et al. (2018) employed cluster analysis to assess CPs' relevance for temperature fluctuations in tropical North Africa. Batté et al. (2018) used CPs to predict West African Heat Waves at both subseasonal and seasonal timescales. They proposed that these CP classifications might be integrated into a hybrid statistical-dynamical forecasting method. Instead of using direct model outputs for temperature, this method uses the ECMWF's SEAS5 forecasted CP-frequency anomalies to generate temperature anomaly forecasts. However, their findings also indicated that this technique needs further improvement. In contrast, Rust et al. (2013) demonstrated that when large-scale CPs are incorporated into their statistical regression model, there is an enhancement in the predictive ability for both the occurrence and amount of rainfall in Senegal. Bliefernicht et al. (2022a) introduced a two-step atmospheric CP classification for West Africa, focusing on both seasonal and daily rainfall variability in the Sudan-Sahel zone (Burkina Faso). As predictor variables, they used mean sea level pressure for the seasonal classification and the stream function fields at 700 hPa to better account for daily rainfall variability. Recently, Nkrumah et al. (2023) identified nine CPs over West Africa and investigated changes associated with favorable environments for mesoscale convective systems using Self-Organizing Maps (SOMs) based on the 925 hPa geopotential height. While the aforementioned studies have primarily addressed CP classifications and their effects on daily variability, this study builds upon the work of Bliefernicht et al. (2022a) and specifically targets CPs indicative of interannual variability.

However, the availability of in-situ observations remains a persistent challenge (Salack et al. 2019, Bliefernicht et al. 2022b). Such data are crucial for establishing the relationships between regional-scale atmospheric patterns (predictors) and local weather variables (predictands). Despite significant progress in the development of improved meteorological networks through various initiatives (van de Giesen et al. 2014, Galle et al. 2018, Bliefernicht et al. 2018, Schunke et al. 2021, Sawadogo et al. 2023), the scarcity of long-term in-situ observations continues to inhibit the development of reliable statistical approaches in the region. In response to these challenges, our study proposes several key contributions to enhance the understanding of interannual rainfall variability in West Africa through the development of a CP-based statistical adaptation approach. Therefore, our research is directed towards achieving three key objectives:

- Establishment of an improved rainfall dataset for the West Africa region based on long-term in-situ observations.
- Development of historical catalogues of daily CP classifications using pre-selected atmospheric variables for different climate zones.
- Introduction of a straightforward method that uses daily CPs to reconstruct interannual rainfall anomalies.

The article is structured as follows: Section 2 provides an overview of the study area and rainfall data with a particular focus on the ERA-5 dataset and the extensive network of rainfall stations across West Africa. Section 3 outlines the methodological workflow. This includes an explanation of the clustering method, the multi-class logistic regression, and the validation of the latter. Section 4 presents the results, including a special focus on the Sahelian belt. Section 5 offers a discussion of the results, and Section 6 provides a key summary.

2 | STUDY AREA AND DATA

2.1 | Study Area

The focus of this study is on West Africa, with special emphasis on the Sahelian belt—a zone dependent on the dynamics of the WAM. The WAM is characterized by a complex interplay of atmospheric, oceanic, and terrestrial forces. A strong influence on the monsoon's northward progression during the boreal summer is the thermal gradient established between the landmass of the African continent and the relatively cooler Atlantic and Mediterranean Seas. As the land heats up due to seasonally driven insolation changes, the associated temperature differences amplify, leading to a northward shift of the low-level pressure gradient. This shift plays a central role in the seasonal rainfall distribution and the overall seasonal cycle in West Africa.

Central atmospheric features in the WAM region include the Saharan Heat Low (SHL), the Intertropical Discontinuity (ITD), the African Easterly Jet (AEJ), the Intertropical Convergence Zone (ITCZ), the Tropical Easterly Jet (TEJ), and the AEWs (Lafore et al. 2010, Nicholson 2009, Fink et al. 2016). These features, each with its unique impact on the WAM, play crucial roles in determining rainfall patterns. For instance, Sheen et al. (2017) point out the significance of certain elements, such as the convergence of southern monsoon winds with northern Mediterranean winds, in enhancing rainfall. Enhanced rainfall is also associated with a more potent TEJ positioned further north and a strengthened AEJ (Grist and Nicholson 2001). The West African Westerly Jet (WAWJ), a low-level westerly jet located between 8°N and 11°N over the West African coast and the Atlantic, plays a pivotal role in moisture transport into the Sahel (Pu and Cook 2010). Thorncroft et al. (2011) emphasize the SHL and the Atlantic equatorial cold tongue's role in moisture fluxes and subsequent rainfall. Moreover, the variability in West African summer rainfall is heavily influenced by the equatorial Atlantic Sea Surface Temperature (Fontaine and Bigot 1993, Fontaine and Janicot 1996, Vizi and Cook 2002, Reason and Rouault 2006, Losada et al. 2010).

In essence, the WAM is a complex system characterized by interactions between zonal features such as the WAWJ, AEJ, and TEJ, and meridional elements like southerly monsoon winds, northerly Mediterranean winds, and convergence zones. The strength, positioning, and interplay of these WAM features are pivotal in determining rainfall quantity and its variability across the region. Given the evident relationships between these regional-scale atmospheric processes and meteorological variables, there is a strong motivation for their use in statistical adaptation of model outputs. Harnessing these relationships allows us to infer local-scale phenomena from larger-scale atmospheric conditions.

2.2 | Rainfall Data

The in-situ daily rainfall records were sourced from two databases: the KASS-D (Karlsruhe Surface Station Database, indicated in red in Figure 1, 1810 stations) and a daily subset of the the WAHPD (West African Historical Precipitation Database, indicated in blue in Figure 1, 410 stations). The WAHPD is described in Bliedernicht et al. (2022b), providing information on data sources and the quality algorithms applied. Furthermore, these databases have been used in various other studies, e.g., Bliedernicht et al. (2022a), Ascott et al. (2020) for WAHPD, and Schlueter et al. (2019), Vogel et al. (2018) for KASS-D. In order to cover a significant portion of Africa north of the equator, the data selection focuses on the region between 18°W to 10°E longitude and 4°N to 20°N latitude (see Predictand in Figure 1, WAHPD: 299 stations, KASS-D: 1467 stations) and spans an overall period from 1959 to 2010. To ensure an adequate data sample for meaningful analysis, time series are required to have a minimum of 5 years of data (WAHPD: 276 stations, KASS-D: 1099 stations).

To merge the KASS-D and WAHPD datasets (1375 stations), a multi-step approach is necessary. Initially, we address the discrepancies in time stamps between the datasets. The norm for daily rainfall measurements is a 24-hour period, from 06:00 UTC to 06:00 UTC, but real-world inconsistencies often occur due to factors like local time zones, station-specific data collection practices, and occasional errors in recording or reporting. For KASS-D, stations assign date stamps for daily accumulated rainfall observations from 06:00 UTC to 06:00 UTC to the subsequent day (Maranan 2023, personal communication). This practice deviates from the WAHPD database alignment. To reconcile this, we consider shifting the WAHPD time series by one day, aligning it with the KASS-D time stamps. We then evaluate the correlation between the adjusted WAHPD data and nearby stations within a 50 km radius. If a significant improvement in correlation (> 0.5) is observed, suggesting a closer agreement with nearby stations, the respective WAHPD station's data is shifted by one day for better alignment.

Prior to geostatistical analysis, the data undergoes preprocessing: years marked only by dry periods, and stations with only missing values or duplicate coordinates are excluded (1299 stations). This ensures the dataset is free from anomalies like years

with exclusive dry periods and stations with missing or redundant data. By considering the spatial relationships between stations, we can assess the correlation between neighboring stations within a specific distance, which allows us to evaluate the similarity or dissimilarity of rainfall time series and identify any discrepancies between the databases. After acquiring the distance and correlation matrices, several geostatistical steps are performed to filter stations with insufficient data quality. These steps help ensure that the merged dataset includes reliable and representative stations. The following procedures are implemented:

- Highly correlated stations (less than 25 km apart, with a correlation greater than 0.9) were consolidated, retaining the one with more complete data (elimination of 280 stations).
- Poorly correlated nearby stations (less than 25 km apart, with a correlation less than 0.1) were removed (elimination of 25 stations).
- For distant but highly correlated stations (more than 25 km apart, with a correlation greater than 0.9), the station with the lowest correlation among the ten nearest was deleted (elimination of 23 stations).

By applying these geostatistical filtering steps, stations with insufficient data quality or poor spatial consistency are eliminated. The result is a curated dataset of 971 quality-controlled stations with an average station data availability of approximately 44% (Figure 2), underscoring the data scarcity in West Africa. To easily apply statistical techniques such as k-means, an infilled dataset is helpful. To address missing values, we employ a nearest-neighbor (NN) infilling approach. While traditional NN methods depend on Euclidean distance, our approach leans on the highest observed Pearson correlation for the specific station; this approach has outperformed others in our evaluations [not shown]. We draw upon the insights from Pegram et al. (2016), which show that the performance differences between sophisticated statistical methods, such as dynamic copula regression (Bárdossy and Pegram 2014), and simpler NN techniques are minimal. Additional details about the NN infilling methodology can be found in the aforementioned references. Furthermore, NN methods preserve spatial variance more effectively than other interpolation techniques such as ordinary kriging or inverse distance weighting, which tend to cause smoothing. This infilled dataset serves as the foundation for our analysis.

In literature, hard borders at specific latitudes are often employed to delineate the diverse rainfall patterns characterizing the seasonal cycle across West Africa (Omotosho and Abiodun 2007, Akinsanola et al. 2017). While this conventional approach offers simplicity, it may fall short in capturing the interactions of climatic factors and the unique characterization that defines the region's rainfall regimes (RRs). As a shift from this approach, we use a more fluid approach by employing the k-means algorithm to classify the rainfall patterns. This classification is based on standardized anomalies from the monthly sums. First, we aggregated the data into monthly sums. Afterwards, we calculated the standardized anomalies for each station by subtracting the station's long-term mean and then dividing by its standard deviation from the complete monthly time series. Thus, the k-means algorithm uses data from 752 months across 971 stations as input. This analytical framework allows for a nuanced classification of rainfall variability.

These clusters, or RRs, offer representations of distinctive rainfall patterns in the region, thereby providing a better understanding of West Africa's rainfall dynamics. The geographical arrangement of the rainfall stations in relation to the designated RRs is illustrated in Figure 2. Additionally, their corresponding monthly rainfall totals are depicted in Figure 3, while their interannual rainfall variability (target predictand) is presented in Figure 4. Within each RR, we sum the daily rainfall to obtain a regional annual sum, which is then standardized to zero mean and unit variance at the interannual scale. Here is a brief description of each RR:

- **RR1:** Strongly associated with the Sahelian belt, the northernmost region which typically experiences a single, short rainy season spanning from June to September. The interannual variability shows a wet phase starting in 1959, followed by the great Sahel drought from 1968 to the 1990s. The subsequent phase is a period of rainfall recovery since the 1990s (Descroix et al. 2018).
- **RR2:** A transition zone, bridging the Sahelian and Sudanian Zones. The rainfall pattern here reflects its intermediary position, with rainfall totals and season length increasing compared to the Sahelian Zone. This region shows a similar behavior of the interannual rainfall variability to RR1, but the rainfall recovery seems to take longer, with more dry years extending until the early 2000s.
- **RR3:** Pertains predominantly to the Sudanian Zone, which is characterized by a lengthier rainy season extending from May to October. The rainfall is more abundant than in the Sahelian zone. Similar to RR1 and RR2, this region experiences comparable patterns of interannual rainfall variability, but the onset of the dry period is delayed until the early 1970s.

- 160 • **RR4:** Serves as a climatic transition between the Sudanian Zone and the Guinean and Coastal Zones. It experiences a
161 bi-modal rainfall pattern, although the 'August break' and rainfall peaks are less pronounced than in the zones further
162 south. This region has fewer prolonged periods compared to RR1-RR3, indicating an overall more even distribution of the
163 interannual rainfall variability categories.
- 164 • **RR5:** Primarily associated with the Guinean and Coastal Zones, specifically representing the coastal region of Côte d'Ivoire,
165 experiences a unique double peak rainfall pattern due to its geographical proximity to the Atlantic Ocean and equatorial
166 position. The maritime influence and position near the equator cause an extended rainy season with a primary maximum
167 in June and a secondary peak in October. For this coastal region, there is a visual trend towards more normal and dry years
168 from the 1990s to 2010s, with fewer occurrences of wet years.
- 169 • **RR6:** Represents regions like Ghana, Togo, and Benin which exhibit a slightly less pronounced double peak rainfall pattern
170 with lower peaks compared to RR5. This region shows a balance between dry and wet years and a generally more evenly
171 distribution.
- 172 • **RR7:** Represents mostly southern Nigeria, characterized by a less pronounced bimodal RR compared to RR5 or RR6. In
173 this region, a dry phase followed by a recovery from normal to more wet years can be observed.

174 Because the presentation and application of the methodology for each RR are quite extensive, our main focus is on the findings
175 of RR1, with summaries of the other RRs provided in Chapter 4.3.

176 2.3 | ERA-5 Reanalysis

177 The ERA-5 dataset, developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF), represents their
178 most recent reanalysis dataset. It provides comprehensive insights into atmospheric, terrestrial, and oceanic climate variables
179 (Hersbach et al. 2020). For the CP-based regression analysis, ERA-5 serves as a primary source of predictor data. For the
180 analysis, ERA-5 hourly data from 1959 to 2010 was obtained from the Climate Data Store of the Copernicus Climate Change
181 Service. This data was then averaged from an hourly scale to provide daily-scale predictor information. To further optimize
182 computational efficiency, the ERA-5 reanalysis fields were preprocessed to a resolution of $2^\circ \times 2^\circ$. In total, this study uses
183 6 individual variables (SF, U, V, WD, WS, MSLP) on 4 different pressure levels from the ERA-5 dataset. Detailed informa-
184 tion about the variables can be found in Table 1. The pre-selection of predictor variables in this study is based on existing
185 literature, aligning with the studies by Moron et al. (2008a) (U/V200, U/V700, U/V925), Guèye et al. (2011 2012) (U/V850),
186 and Bliefernicht et al. (2022a) (U/V at multiple levels, SF700, SF850). MSLP is also commonly employed (Guèye et al. 2011
187 2012, Bliefernicht et al. 2022a). Additionally, every possible combination of these variables up to four is considered, leading
188 to $C(21, 2) + C(21, 3) + C(21, 4) = 7525$ combinations. As a result, a total of 7546 initial predictor combinations are assessed.

To describe dominant regional-scale features of the WAM (e.g. SHL, TEJ or AEJ), we use a domain spanning from 30°W to 40°E and 5°S to 40°N (see predictor in Figure 1). This coverage encompasses a majority of the regions in Africa located north of the equator, aligning precisely with the domain size used by Bliefernicht et al. (2022a). To prepare the data for modeling, a data scaling preprocessing step was executed. This step involved the normalization of the variables' range. Specifically, standardized anomalies, represented as $z(i, t)$, were derived from the predictor data $x(i, t)$ according to:

$$z(i, t) = \frac{x(i, t) - \bar{x}(i)}{s(i)} \quad (1)$$

189 In this equation, $i = 1, \dots, L$ pertains to the grid points, $t = 1, \dots, T$ denotes the time steps in days, $\bar{x}(i)$ signifies the time-inclusive
190 long-term mean, and $s(i)$ indicates the standard deviation of the time series. This means standardized unfiltered (i.e., the annual
191 cycle is kept) daily anomalies are used for the analysis.

192 In addition to the atmospheric data, the variable of total precipitation at the original resolution of $0.25^\circ \times 0.25^\circ$ has been
193 used to benchmark the proposed CP-based logistic regression model. No further preprocessing steps were applied.

194 3 | METHODS

195 To capture the relationships between selected predictors and desired outcomes, a multi-data preparation pipeline was designed.
196 As shown in Figure 5, the methodology diverges into two branches: one to process atmospheric predictor data and the other

197 focusing on the different RRs over the West African continent. For the atmospheric data, the following steps were undertaken
198 to prepare the predictors for modeling:

- 199 1. **Standardization:** The initial step involved transforming the predictors into anomaly-based variables, as detailed in Eq. 1.
- 200 2. **CP Classification:** The clustering techniques k-means was deployed. The aim was to generate a time series of daily CPs.
- 201 3. **Frequency Computation:** Post-classification, the occurrence frequencies of each CP were standardized and calculated on
202 an annual basis.
- 203 4. **Setup of a Regression Model:** The computed CP frequencies served as predictor variables in a subsequent multi-class
204 logistic regression analysis.

205 For processing and integrating the rainfall data (predictand), the methodology consisted of:

- 206 1. **Data Integration:** The different sources (WAHPD, KASS-D) of rainfall data were prepared and merged.
- 207 2. **Station-based Averaging:** Rainfall records from multiple stations within the chosen region were aggregated to obtain an
208 average areal rainfall measure. This average areal rainfall is then aggregated to yearly sums, denoted as R_A .
- 209 3. **Categorization:** This R_A value was then discretized into ordinal classes using two quantile thresholds (q_1 and q_2). The
210 classes were categorized as follows:
 - 211 • $R_A \leq q_1$: Class 1, signifying a ‘dry’ condition.
 - 212 • $q_1 < R_A < q_2$: Class 2, indicative of a ‘normal’ condition.
 - 213 • $R_A \geq q_2$: Class 3, representing a ‘wet’ condition.
 Here, q_1 is the 0.33th quantile and q_2 is the 0.66th quantile.
- 215 4. **Preparation for Regression:** These categorizations then became the target variables in the multi-class logistic regression
216 model.

217 Detailed discussions on important methodological steps follow in the subsequent sections.

218 3.1 | k-means

219 The k-means algorithm is a widely used clustering algorithm in atmospheric sciences (Huth et al. 2008, Govender and Sivakumar
220 2020), designed to group data by dividing samples into K distinct clusters, each characterized by similar variance levels. The
221 prerequisite for this algorithm is the pre-determination of the number of clusters. In k-means clustering, a set of N samples,
222 denoted as X , is divided into K non-overlapping clusters C . These clusters are defined by their mean μ_j , known as the cluster’s
223 centroid. The primary objective of k-means is to determine centroids that minimize inertia, the within-cluster sum-of-squares
224 criterion, represented as:

$$\sum_{i=0}^n \min_{\mu_j \in C} (\|x_i - \mu_j\|^2) \quad (2)$$

225 For classifying the standardized anomalies of the predictors, we used the MiniBatchKMeans algorithm from scikit-learn
226 (Pedregosa et al. 2012), an efficient adaptation of the traditional k-means. MiniBatchKMeans reduces computational time by
227 processing mini-batches – smaller, randomly selected data subsets – in each iteration. This method significantly lowers the
228 computational load required for converging to a local solution. Although this technique compromises the algorithm’s accuracy,
229 MiniBatchKMeans maintains high-quality outputs, typically with only marginal deviations from the standard k-means results.
230 The k-means++ initialization method (Arthur and Vassilvitskii 2007) was used for robust centroid selection, which aids in
231 faster convergence. To effectively uncover atmospheric CPs, we experimented with cluster counts ranging from 5 to 15.

232 3.2 | Multi-Class Logistic Regression Model

233 Logistic regression is widely used in many atmospheric applications (Gijben et al. 2017, Moon et al. 2019, Moon and Kim 2020).
234 It offers a method of modeling a categorical dependent variable based on one or more independent variables. Unlike linear

regression, which estimates continuous outputs, logistic regression focuses on predicting binary outcomes using the logistic function. In our implementation, the computed frequencies of the CPs on an annual basis were used as predictor variables, while the classes – dry, normal, or wet – were used as the predictand variables.

Given a set of predictors X_1, X_2, \dots, X_p , the logistic regression model expresses the probability $P(Y = 1)$ as:

$$P(Y = 1|X) = \frac{e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_p X_p}}{1 + e^{\beta_0 + \beta_1 X_1 + \dots + \beta_p X_p}} \quad (3)$$

where $\beta_0, \beta_1, \dots, \beta_p$ are coefficients that the model seeks to estimate. Given the multi-class nature of the dependent variable, a conventional binary logistic regression model would be insufficient. To address this, the study employed the One-vs-Rest (OVR) strategy combined with logistic regression to perform multi-class classification. The OVR approach inherently breaks down a multi-class classification problem into multiple binary classification tasks. For a dataset with n classes, n distinct binary classifiers are trained. For each classifier, one class is treated as the positive class, while all other classes are treated as the negative class. In this study, the LogisticRegression function from the scikit-learn library was used (Pedregosa et al. 2012).

3.3 | Validation and Performance Measures

To evaluate the performance of our multi-class logistic regression model, we use two different metrics: Proportion Correct (PC) and Peirce Skill Score (PSS). These metrics are implemented in accordance with the guidelines provided by Wilks (2006). For additional information on these performance measures, the cited work offers an in-depth discussion. The performance measures are derived from a 3x3 contingency table. The PC is the most straightforward metric, computed as the sum of the diagonal elements (correct hindcasts) divided by the total number of joint hindcast and observation pairs in a 3x3 contingency table. As pointed out by Grandini et al. (2020), the PC is particularly suitable for balanced datasets. In the tercile-based approach of this study, the balanced nature of the dataset ensures that the metric is not biased towards any specific class. A shortcoming of the PC is that no comparison is done versus a low skill reference. That is the reason why the PSS is chosen in addition to the PC to determine the skill of the reconstruction. The equation for the PSS is as follows:

$$PSS = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^I p(y_i, o_i) - \sum_{i=1}^I p(y_i)p(o_i)}{1 - \sum_{j=1}^J p(o_j)^2} \quad (4)$$

Here, $p(y_i, o_i)$ represents the joint probability of hindcasts and observations, while $p(y_i)$ and $p(o_j)$ are the marginal distributions of hindcasts and observations, respectively. I and J denote the number of categories for hindcast and observations. The PSS aims to quantify the hindcast skill while accounting for random chance. A perfect hindcast would result in PC and PSS scores of 1. Conversely, a hindcast no better than random chance would yield PSS scores of 0 and zero hits for PC. Negative PSS scores indicate a hindcast worse than random chance.

In atmospheric sciences, a variety of methods are used to assess the quality of regression models that link predictors and predictands. A key aspect of this validation process is choosing appropriate training and validation periods. This choice is crucial to avoid overfitting and ensure the reliability of the model. To achieve this, techniques like split-sampling (Bárdossy et al. 2002), cross-validation (Rust et al. 2013, Gutiérrez et al. 2019), stratified validation (Zeng and Martinez 2000), and statistical model ensembles (Hertig and Jacobeit 2008) can be applied. Particularly, the latter technique employs multiple statistical models across different training and validation periods to avoid artificial skill and address non-stationarities in predictor-predictand dynamics (Hertig and Jacobeit 2013). These non-stationarities occur on varying temporal and spatial scales, with the El Niño–Southern Oscillation being a well-documented example that significantly affects global climate (Janicot et al. 1996, Greatbatch et al. 2004, Cannon 2015).

This work is based on a 2/3 to 1/3 running split-sampling method, allocating 39 years for training and 13 years for validation. The complete approach, as illustrated in Figure 5, is applied to all variable combinations and CP number configurations leading to a total of 75.460 potential combinations for each RR in a running calibration mode. In this context, the metrics PC and PSS are calculated for each training (subscript t) and validation (subscript v) period for a selected period in a split-sampling approach. This period is then subsequently shifted forward by one year for the complete period (1959 to 2010). As the entire time series concludes, years from the start are progressively incorporated. In this study, we begin with a training period from 1959 to 1997, followed by a validation period from 1998 to 2010. Subsequently, we use the years 1960 to 1998 for training and 1959, 1999 to 2010 for validation, incorporating years from the beginning of the time series progressively.

277 The mean metrics \hat{PC} and \hat{PSS} are then computed over the statistical model ensembles. The final configuration is selected
 278 based on its performance during the validation period \hat{PC}_v , as evaluated during the ensemble step. This process ensures that
 279 the initial model solution is both robust and reliable.

280 3.4 | An Approach for Benchmarking

281 Based on the generally poor performance of GCMs for local-scale rainfall and their ability to simulate regional-scale meteo-
 282 rological phenomena, this study adopts the use of the "raw" total precipitation variable from the ERA5 dataset to benchmark
 283 the proposed CP-based logistic regression model. By extracting daily rainfall sums on a point-to-pixel basis from ERA5, we di-
 284 rectly compare our modeled outcomes with the reanalysis model output. This enables a comparative analysis that quantifies the
 285 enhancements our approach brings to rainfall reconstruction in West Africa, as opposed to the often used ERA5. We follow the
 286 same data preparation steps (averaging and categorization in RRs) and validation measures (PC , PSS) as described in Section 3.

287 4 | RESULTS

288 The following section first discusses the optimal parsimonious set of variables crucial for accurately reconstructing interannual
 289 rainfall anomalies in the WAM region. It then presents a quality assessment of the CP-based multi-class logistic regression
 290 model of the best solution, with a particular focus on the Sahelian belt (RR1) as a case study. This assessment encompasses
 291 an in-depth examination of the spatial composite of the selected CPs, their meteorological interpretation, CP statistics, the
 292 coefficients of the regression model, and a predictive analysis of interannual rainfall variability in the Sahel. Subsequently, the
 293 last chapter provides a brief summary of the other RRs.

294 4.1 | Identifying the Optimal Parsimonious Set of Variables for Interannual Rainfall Recon- 295 struction

296 This section focuses on identifying the most effective combination of atmospheric variables for reconstructing interannual
 297 rainfall in the RR1 region. We employ our methodology (Figure 5) to evaluate different variable combinations and determine
 298 which combination captures the essential dynamics influencing regional rainfall with the highest accuracy and efficiency.

299 Table 2 shows the best-performing models for each specific class of variable combinations, ranging from 1 to 4 variables.
 300 It reveals that the single variable WS200 delivers comparatively robust performance metrics. Specifically, WS200 as single
 301 variable achieved a \hat{PC}_t of 0.627 and a \hat{PSS}_t of 0.449, with the validation metrics standing at 0.602 and 0.244 respectively.
 302 When additional variables are included, the improvements in both \hat{PC} and \hat{PSS} are marginal.

303 Therefore, just a single variable and the solution of WS200 for RR1 is chosen due to its superior performance, simplicity,
 304 and lower computational demands compared to models using multiple variables. The slight improvements offered by additional
 305 variables do not outweigh the benefits of a parsimonious model, which adheres to the principle of achieving a similar level of
 306 skill scores (PC , PSS) with the least complexity.

307 4.2 | Sahelian Belt – RR1

308 Given the availability of solutions from 52 models (one for each shifted year) for the k-means clustering applied to the WS200
 309 variable under six CPs, we chose to showcase an extraordinary case marked by an exceptionally high PC_v . This particular
 310 model underwent training during two separate intervals: from 1959 to 1977 and from 1991 to 2010. The validation period for
 311 the model covered the years from 1978 to 1990, a period notable for the great Sahel drought. During these phases, the model
 312 achieved the following performance measures: $PC_t = 0.59$, $PSS_t = 0.39$, $PC_v = 0.85$, and $PSS_v = 0.59$.

313 Figure 6 shows the composites of the spatial CPs from WS200 anomalies which signify changes in wind speed in the upper
 314 troposphere, around an altitude of 12 km, often associated with the TEJ. The relationship between the TEJ and rainfall activity
 315 in the Sahel is well-documented (Lemburg et al. 2019, Nicholson and Klotter 2021). CP1, CP2, CP3 mainly occur in the
 316 northern hemisphere's winter and spring months. Their occurrence decreases in April and reaches a minimum in May and

317 October. The CPs are almost completely absent from June to September (Figure 7). The WS200 fields exhibit strong positive
318 anomalies over the West African continent, which may be attributed to the strong westerly flow of the subtropical jet stream in
319 winter (Krishnamurti 1961). During this period, the TEJ develops in the southern hemisphere, extending between the equator
320 and 10°S (Nicholson and Klotter 2021), and is therefore mostly outside our predictor domain (Figure 1).

321 As the seasonal cycle progresses, key atmospheric features such as the TEJ migrate northward, in alignment with the sun's
322 zenith position. Specifically, CP4 primarily occurs in May, October and November, while being completely absent in July and
323 August (Figure 7). This pattern is further illustrated by the spatial reduction of positive anomalies and the emergence of higher
324 negative anomalies in the WS200 fields (Figure 6). Moreover, the rainfall intensity is slightly increased when compared to CP1,
325 CP2, and CP3 (Table 3).

326 CP5 and CP6 are primarily observed during the main monsoon period. CP5 occurs prominently in June with an average du-
327 ration of 21 days (Figure 7). Notably, there is a slight positive anomaly at 0°N in the WS200 fields, which suggests a potentially
328 weakened TEJ. CP6 exhibits a very specific temporal pattern, appearing only from June to August, but with a very high fre-
329 quency, peaking at over 26 days in both July and August. This phase is characterized by pronounced positive WS200 anomalies
330 around the Equator, indicating a strengthened TEJ, which typically signifies intense upper tropospheric winds. However, for a
331 comprehensive analysis, it is crucial to evaluate the zonal wind component at this altitude to determine whether these anomalies
332 correspond to a strengthened or weakened TEJ.

333 Table 3 summarizes the behavior of the six CPs under three tercile-based categories: dry, normal, and wet years and the
334 climatology. Three key metrics evaluate each category: the overall occurrence percentage [%] and the mean rainfall (R_A [mm])
335 and the respective anomaly. In general, CP6 exhibits the highest amounts of rainfall, followed by CP5. Conversely, CP1 to CP4
336 show almost no rainfall (< 1 mm). CP1 is less common in wet years (-15.39%), while CP2 is less common in dry years (-12.39%).
337 CP3 and CP4 are fairly stable across the different categories. In contrast, CP5 and CP6 exhibit significant variability, indicating
338 greater sensitivity to rainfall variability. The occurrence of CP5 reduces considerably in wet years, dropping by -16.79%, which
339 suggests it is less prevalent in wetter conditions. This decrease in both occurrence and rainfall amounts reveals CP5's sensitivity
340 to dry years. On the other hand, CP6 occurs more often in wet years (+14.22%) with enhanced rainfall amounts.

341 Regression coefficients from the multi-class logistic regression model further support these observations (Figure 8). The
342 purpose of these coefficients is to gauge the likelihood of each CP occurring under specific categories, thereby providing an
343 analytical foundation for understanding their climate sensitivity. For CP5, coefficients are positive during dry (0.36) but negative
344 during wet years (-0.47), aligning with its occurrence data. For CP6, a negative coefficient during dry years (-0.69) and a
345 positive one during wet years (0.57) indicate its high importance for these years. The coefficients for both CP5 and CP6 largely
346 agree with their occurrence percentages and rainfall amounts, reinforcing their roles as key CPs for the rainy season in the
347 Sahelian belt. Winter CPs indicating a dry year tend to persist longer. The findings from the logistic regression model support
348 this hypothesis. CP1 exerts a positive impact (0.21) on dry conditions when it occurs more frequently, whereas it has a negative
349 influence (-0.23) on wet conditions when it occurs less frequently. This demonstrates the significant role that winter CPs play.

350 Figure 9 displays the outcomes derived from the multi-class logistic regression model for RR1. This plot shows the model's
351 reconstruction compared to the actual standardized annual rainfall amounts from 1959 to 2010. The grey continuous line shows
352 the real values of standardized annual rainfall sums. The two dashed lines represent the terciles which cut the data into three
353 rainfall categories: dry (below the first dashed line), normal (between the two dashed lines), and wet (above the second dashed
354 line). Model hindcasts appear as scatter points: blue circle-markers indicate correct hindcast, while yellow square-markers
355 signify incorrect ones.

356 In the Sahel, two contrasting hydrological behaviors emerged over the past five decades. The first is the great Sahel drought
357 from 1968 to the 1990s, while the second is the subsequent period of rainfall recovery since the 1990s (Descroix et al. 2018)
358 (grey line in Figure 9). These phases are generally well-detected with minor inconsistencies, such as at the beginning of the
359 time series or the years 2007 to 2009. Remarkably, the Sahel drought falls in into the validation period. In summary, built on the
360 foundation of k-means clustering for the WS200 anomalies, this multi-class logistic regression model demonstrates an average
361 $\hat{P}C$ of 0.61 with a reasonable meteorological interpretation. This makes it a statistical tool for reconstructing annual rainfall
362 amounts with respect to the Sahelian belt.

363 4.3 | Overall Performance and Benchmarking

364 Table 4 provides an overview of the validation performance for each RR, the top-performing variable, their respective CP num-
365 bers, training and validation metrics. The RRs display balanced performance metrics between training and validation phases

relative to RR1. The CP count varies across the regions, with values ranging from 5 to 14. Due to space constraints, a comprehensive presentation of results for each RR is beyond the scope of this paper. Therefore, we primarily focused on presenting the findings of RR1 as a representative case study.

Additionally, we evaluate the performance of our approach against the total precipitation variable from ERA5, serving as a benchmark (PC_{ERA5} and PSS_{ERA5} in Table 4). It is shown that our approach either outperforms or achieves comparable performance to that of ERA5 across all regions. Specifically, the proposed CP-based logistic model demonstrates an average performance with a PC of 0.57 and a PSS of 0.32. In contrast, ERA5 yields values of 0.46 and 0.18, respectively. Overall, a performance enhancement of more than 28% on average in terms of PC can be achieved, despite the relatively modest performance of both.

5 | DISCUSSION

This study followed a straight-forward statistical approach based on CPs to reconstruct interannual rainfall variability in West Africa. The further development of this study focuses on a comprehensive application covering the entire WAM region. It takes into account the variability across different RRs, relying on a long-term dataset spanning 61 years. Our approach establishes a robust catalogue of daily CP classification which can be used for further refinement and offers greater flexibility to tackle specific research questions.

However, it is important to note that year-to-year changes in CP frequencies cannot fully account for the interannual variability of rainfall. Even if the frequency of a specific CP remains constant, it may still be associated with wetter conditions in some years than in others. For subsequent research, it could be beneficial to delineate between high-frequency and low-frequency fluctuations—for instance, by categorizing variations as either shorter or longer than a decade. This distinction is important because low-frequency (long-term) variations typically demonstrate greater predictability compared to their high-frequency (short-term) counterparts. Such a separation could provide deeper insights into the dynamics influencing rainfall variability and enhance the accuracy of hindcasting efforts.

A study by Batté et al. (2018) also used a statistical-dynamical forecasting approach similar to ours. They employed forecasted CP-frequency anomalies from the ECMWF SEAS5 to construct temperature anomaly forecasts. Interestingly, they found no significant skill in predicting CP frequency at a seasonal timescale, a finding that should be evaluated in future for our models. This underscores the complexity of climate systems in the WAM region and highlights the challenges of seasonal forecasting for meteorological variables. Beyond their indirect utility, such as using CP frequencies for analyses, CPs can be included as additional covariates in regression models to directly model rainfall (Rust et al. 2013). They can also be used in conjunction with other techniques, such as canonical correlation analysis (Moron et al. 2008a). Furthermore, CPs can serve in an analog method (Zorita and von Storch 1999), wherein CPs simulated by climate models (e.g., CMIP6) are matched with local variables observed in conjunction with similar CPs from historical observations. For instance, this could allow us to more accurately predict the distribution of extreme values in future climate projections, which is crucial for understanding the risks associated with severe weather events. Additionally, our catalog of classification schemes can be swiftly accessed and utilized for further regression tasks, thereby providing a valuable resource for future research.

The application of k-means clustering to delineate different RRs might be an overly broad generalization for these diverse areas, particularly considering our initial choice of regionalization based on the mean annual cycle, which may not fully capture the complexity of interannual variability. While the differentiation in Burkina Faso aligns well with the latitudinal subjective categorization into the Sahelian zone, Sudano-Sahelian zone, and Sudanian zone as described by Garba et al. (2023), the longitudinal differentiation within regions like the Sahelian belt (RR1) poses challenges. For instance, projections of future rainfall patterns suggest that the central-eastern Sahel will experience increased rainfall, while the western Sahel will likely see a decrease (Monerie et al. 2012, Akinsanola and Zhou 2019). These distinctions, usually found between Eastern Senegal and Central Mali, are not visible in our analysis based on the mean annual cycle, questioning the efficacy of our chosen regionalization approach for capturing the targeted interannual variability. This oversight underscores the need for a more nuanced approach that can account for both latitudinal and longitudinal variations in rainfall patterns, beyond the averaging of weather station data across the respective RRs.

The methodology used to define regional rainfall indices is a pivotal aspect of our analysis. It involves aggregating daily rainfall data within each cluster (RR) by mean to then obtain a regional annual sum, which is standardized to zero mean and unit variance on an interannual scale. This method was primarily selected for its potential to illuminate inter-cluster variations

414 and trends over an extended period. However, this approach may inadvertently emphasize the contributions of the wettest
415 stations within each region. Such stations, due to their higher rainfall totals, can disproportionately influence the regional index,
416 potentially skewing the interpretation of regional rainfall characteristics. This issue is particularly critical as it may lead to an
417 overestimation of wet conditions in regions that are otherwise more variably characterized by both dry and wet extremes. A
418 better approach would be to standardize the annual rainfall at each station prior to calculating the average for the cluster. This
419 method has the advantage of normalizing the input from all stations, thereby mitigating the influence of outliers and emphasizing
420 years when rainfall anomalies are spatially consistent across the region. This could provide a more balanced view of regional
421 climate patterns, especially in studies focused on interannual predictability where understanding spatially coherent anomalies
422 is crucial.

423 The annual changes in Sahel rainfall amounts cannot be adequately explained by just one predictor variable. However, these
424 rainfall patterns seem strongly influenced by anomalies in both planetary and regional atmospheric circulation. Given that these
425 primary drivers operate on a large scale and are therefore well-captured by climate models, there is a level of confidence in
426 future climate projections for the Sahel (Biasutti 2019).

427 6 | SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

428 This research provides an approach for a statistical tool using atmospheric circulation patterns to effectively reconstruct interan-
429 nual rainfall variability in West Africa. This method integrates a reliable dataset of rainfall and atmospheric circulation patterns,
430 offering a comprehensive view of the factors influencing rainfall.

431 We sourced information from 971 rainfall stations covering a broad geographical range (18°W to 10°E longitude and 4°N to
432 20°N latitude) spanning from 1959 to 2010. Our study categorizes rainfall stations into distinct regimes representing different
433 climatic zones, from the Sahelian Zone with a short rainy season to Nigeria's bimodal rainfall regime. The ERA-5 dataset served
434 as our primary source of predictor data, with six pre-selected variables.

435 Our methodology involved several crucial steps to ensure data quality and contextual relevance. We standardized the pre-
436 dictors into anomaly-based measures, classified daily atmospheric circulation patterns using k-means, and established a robust
437 historical catalogue for multiple relevant variables. After classification, we calculated the annual occurrence frequencies of each
438 label, which then served as predictor variables in a multi-class logistic regression analysis. Our final solutions showed an av-
439 erage correct proportion of 0.57 and positive Peirce skill scores for all regions, mostly outperforming the TP variable from the
440 ERA5 dataset. This makes it a valuable tool for reconstructing annual rainfall across various West African regimes. To address
441 non-stationarities and avoid overfitting, we incorporated an extensive validation framework with statistical model ensembles
442 using running training and validation periods.

443 Focusing specifically on the Sahelian belt, the study highlights two contrasting hydrological behaviors over the past five
444 decades: the great Sahel drought (1968 to the 1990s) and the subsequent rainfall recovery since the 1990s. These periods are
445 linked to TEJ. Wet years show high frequency with significant positive anomalies in upper air wind speed (200 hPa), indicating
446 a strong TEJ and intense upper tropospheric winds, while dry years show a slight positive anomaly, suggesting a potentially
447 weakened TEJ. Thus, we have directly combined atmospheric characteristics with the annual rainfall anomalies in this difficult
448 region.

449 In summary, our key results are:

- 450 ● A quality-controlled and infilled dataset of 971 rainfall stations spanning from 1959 to 2010 for the data-scarce West African
451 region.
- 452 ● A nuanced classification of seven rainfall regimes, from the Sahelian belt to the Guinea zone.
- 453 ● A robust catalogue of daily atmospheric circulation pattern classifications.
- 454 ● A straightforward statistical method using daily circulation patterns to reconstruct interannual rainfall anomalies across
455 seven rainfall regimes.

456 Furthermore, the presented work opens up numerous possibilities for statistical applications in climate science and other
457 disciplines within the WAM region. For example, the target can be easily shifted from the interannual variability to other
458 applications (e.g. the onset of the rainy season (Rauch et al. 2019)), thereby enhancing the understanding of rainfall or other
459 meteorological variables in this challenging region.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Manuel Rauch: Conceptualization, Methodology, Software, Data curation, Investigation, Validation, Formal analysis, Visualization, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing. Jan Bliedernicht: Conceptualization, Methodology, Data curation, Validation, Supervision, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Formal analysis, Resources. Harald Kunstmann: Writing - original draft, Writing - review & editing, Funding acquisition, Project administration.

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The tools MiniBatchKMeans and Logistic Regression are from the scikit-learn library (Pedregosa et al. 2012). Data processing, handling, and manipulation were done with xarray (Hoyer and Hamman 2017), numpy (Harris et al. 2020), pandas (McKinney 2010), and ray for parallel processing (Moritz et al. 2017). Figure 1 and Figure 2 were created using QGIS. Figure 3, Figure 4, Figure 6, Figure 7, Figure 8 and Figure 9 were generated using matplotlib (Hunter 2007). Figure 5 was generated using the TikZpicture package. Manuscript drafting and formatting were done in LaTeX on the Overleaf platform. ChatGPT-4 assisted with spell-checking and grammar improvement.

FINANCIAL DISCLOSURE

None reported.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no potential conflict of interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The in-situ rainfall records were sourced from KASS-D and the WAHPD, neither of which is publicly accessible. The ERA-5 reanalysis dataset was obtained from the Climate Data Store of the Copernicus Climate Change Service (Hersbach et al. 2023ab). The CP classification data can be made available upon request by contacting the corresponding author and will be uploaded into the WASCAL Data Infrastructure (WADI, <https://wascal-dataportal.org/>).

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

None reported.

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FIGURE 1 Distribution of the rainfall stations across the study area in West Africa, with the locations of WAHPD (West African Historical Precipitation Database, red) stations and KASS-D (Karlsruhe Surface Station Database, blue) stations. The box labeled "Predictand" denotes the target region for the chosen rainfall data, whereas the broader area labeled "Predictor" represents the target region for the reanalysis data (ERA-5).

FIGURE 2 Geographical distribution of rainfall stations across West Africa, classified into seven Rainfall Regimes (RRs) using the k-means algorithm based on monthly rainfall anomalies. Each RR represents a unique rainfall pattern, surpassing the traditional latitude-based distinctions: **RR1** - Sahelian Zone, **RR2** - Transition between Sahelian and Sudanian Zones, **RR3** - Sudanian Zone, **RR4** - Transition between Sudanian, Guinean and Coastal Zones, **RR5** - Guinean and Coastal Zones, Côte d'Ivoire, **RR6** - Guinean and Coastal Zones, Ghana, Togo, and Benin, and **RR7** - Guinean and Coastal Zones, Nigeria.

FIGURE 3 Averaged monthly rainfall sums [mm] for the seven Rainfall Regimes (RRs). See Figure 2 for an overview of the different RRs.

FIGURE 4 Averaged standardized interannual rainfall variability for the seven RRs. See Figure 2 for an overview of the different RRs. The continuous black line represents the actual values of standardized annual rainfall sums, with the two dashed lines denoting the 0.33 and 0.66 quantiles, which segment the data into three categories: dry (dark orange circle, below the first dashed line), normal (red square, between the two dashed lines), and wet (blue diamond, above the second dashed line).

FIGURE 5 Flowchart illustrating the multifaceted approach to reconstruct rainfall anomalies in the West African region. The flowchart is divided into two main branches: the left one focusing on atmospheric data and the right one on Rainfall Regions (RR). Each branch undergoes a series of transformations and classifications. They converge at a multi-class logistic regression model, which detects whether a year will be dry, normal, or wet.

FIGURE 6 Atmospheric CPs for the WS200 variable as the chosen solution for RR1. The color scale signifies the mean intensity of the measured variable, where red and blue shades represent positive and negative anomalies, respectively. WS200 anomalies are represented only where the anomaly is statistically significant at the 1% level (or 99% confidence level) computed with a two-tailed t-test.

FIGURE 7 Monthly occurrence frequencies in days for each CP of the classification using WS200.

FIGURE 8 Heat map of coefficients from the multi-class logistic regression model for RR1. The color coding indicates the importance of each CP for dry, normal, or wet years.

FIGURE 9 Outcomes of the CP-based multi-class logistic regression model for the interannual rainfall variability in RR1. The continuous line represents the actual values of standardized annual rainfall sums, with the two dashed lines denoting the 0.33 and 0.66 quantiles, which segment the data into three categories: dry (below the first dashed line), normal (between the two dashed lines), and wet (above the second dashed line). Predictions from the regression model are presented as scatter points: 'o' markers in blue represent matches (correct predictions), and 'x' markers in yellow indicate mismatches (incorrect predictions).

TABLE 1 Pressure-level variables: Listing of abbreviations, associated atmospheric pressures, units, and input variables for computation. The designation 'all levels' includes atmospheric pressures at 200hPa, 700hPa, 850hPa, 925hPa. Further information on each variable can be found in Hersbach et al. (2023a) and Hersbach et al. (2023b).

Name	Abbreviation	Levels	Units	Input
Pressure-level variables				
Stream function	SF	all levels	$\text{m}^2 \text{s}^{-1}$	U, V
U-component of wind	U	all levels	m s^{-1}	-
V-component of wind	V	all levels	m s^{-1}	-
Wind direction	WD	all levels	degrees	U, V
Wind speed	WS	all levels	m s^{-1}	U, V
Single-level variables				
Mean sea level pressure	MSLP	-	Pa	-
Total precipitation	TP	-	mm	-

TABLE 2 Evaluation of the optimal variable combinations for interannual rainfall variability reconstruction in RR1. This table identifies the highest-performing combinations of one, two, and three variables, along with the count of CPs, and compares their performance metrics across training and validation phases.

k-means	CPs	$\hat{P}C_t$	$P\hat{S}S_t$	$\hat{P}C_v$	$P\hat{S}S_v$
WS200	6	0.627	0.449	0.602	0.244
WS200, SF200	7	0.640	0.466	0.612	0.276
U200, V200, WS200	7	0.652	0.485	0.620	0.263
U200, V700, WS200, SF200	7	0.637	0.463	0.623	0.284

TABLE 3 Occurrence and rainfall statistics of the CPs in RR with respect to climatology, dry, normal, and wet years (1959-2010). Abbreviations: Occ.: Occurrence [%], R_A : Spatially averaged rainfall amount [mm], Ano.: Anomaly [%] with respect to the climatology. A χ^2 -test assessed the statistical significance between observed (O) and expected (E) frequencies from climatology. All categories (dry, wet, and normal) showed p-values below 0.05, rejecting the null hypothesis (H_0) that O equals E , indicating significant differences in all cases.

CP	Climatology		Dry years			Normal years			Wet years		
	Occ. [%]	R_A [mm]	Occ. [%]	R_A [mm]	Ano. [%]	Occ. [%]	R_A [mm]	Ano. [%]	Occ. [%]	R_A [mm]	Ano. [%]
1	14.99	0.03	16.66	0.03	10.00	14.22	0.02	-5.42	12.99	0.02	-15.39
2	12.80	0.03	11.34	0.03	-12.86	14.48	0.02	11.61	13.31	0.03	3.84
3	16.35	0.09	17.04	0.08	4.07	15.39	0.13	-6.24	16.30	0.09	-0.29
4	19.05	0.38	18.86	0.36	-1.02	18.42	0.31	-3.45	20.18	0.49	5.56
5	18.38	1.88	20.22	1.78	9.12	17.87	1.88	-2.82	15.73	2.13	-16.79
6	18.43	3.97	15.88	3.31	-16.08	19.62	4.21	6.06	21.48	4.57	14.22

TABLE 4 Evaluation of the performance by region. The table presents the best-performing variables for each region based on the performance criterion $P\hat{C}_v$, along with the count of CPs and the evaluation metrics for both training ($P\hat{C}_t$, $P\hat{S}S_t$) and validation ($P\hat{C}_v$, $P\hat{S}S_v$) phases. The values of PC_{ERA5} and PSS_{ERA5} show the performance of ERA5.

RR	Variable	CPs	$P\hat{C}_t$	$P\hat{C}_v$	$P\hat{C}_{t,v}$	PC_{ERA5}	Diff.PC[%]	$P\hat{S}S_t$	$P\hat{S}S_v$	$P\hat{S}S_{t,v}$	PSS_{ERA5}	Diff. PSS[%]
1	WS200	6	0.63	0.60	0.62	0.44	39.77	0.45	0.24	0.34	0.16	115.62
2	SF925	5	0.58	0.53	0.55	0.56	-0.89	0.37	0.20	0.29	0.34	-16.18
3	U200	6	0.62	0.55	0.58	0.56	4.46	0.43	0.22	0.32	0.34	-4.41
4	V200	14	0.82	0.48	0.65	0.46	41.30	0.73	0.19	0.46	0.19	142.11
5	SF850	6	0.66	0.55	0.60	0.42	44.05	0.49	0.19	0.34	0.13	161.54
6	U925	7	0.60	0.44	0.52	0.37	40.54	0.41	0.13	0.27	0.05	440.00
7	WD925	6	0.55	0.45	0.50	0.38	31.58	0.33	0.11	0.22	0.08	175.00